

PARENT PARTICIPATION IN SCHOOL MANAGEMENT IN PILAS DISTRICT

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Abstract: This study determined the parent participation in school management in Pilas District. The descriptive research method was used. The subjects of the study were the One Hundred Thirty (130) Parents-Teachers Community Association (PTCA) Officers of the Thirteen (13) Public Elementary Schools in Pilas District. A questionnaire was the instrument used in this study. The results of the study were: 1. The parents' level of participation in the management of their child/ren's school, in Curriculum Enhancement is 'Low'; 2. Their levels of participation in School Governance, Community Development, and Student Activities are 'Average'; 3. As a whole, their level of participation in school management is 'Average'; 4. There are no significant differences between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, if the data is grouped according to age and gender; and 5. There are significant differences between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, if the data is grouped according to highest educational attainment.

Keywords: Parent participation, School Management, Curriculum Enhancement, School Governance, Community Development.

I. INTRODUCTION

The basic framework of a quality education system is one that succeeds in meeting the individual school desired goals and outcomes; one that is relevant to the needs of students, communities and society; and one that fosters the ability of students to acquire knowledge and the needed 21st century skills. Improved leadership, administration, planning and budgeting, along with transparency, accountability, and improved parental and community participation, create the conditions for improved and more relevant learning and teaching (Stone, Bruce & Hursh, 2007).

Strengthening school-parent partnerships is recognized as a strategy for addressing learning and achieving the globally agreed education target in the Sustainable Development Goals: inclusive and equitable quality education for all (UNESCO, 2015). It is a pedagogical belief that the inclusion of the parents is one of the crucial tools in achieving better results in the upbringing and educational process, as well as an excellent mechanism for creation of more efficiently and more democratically managed schools (Kostadinova, 2012). Parent participation in school management has been promoted as a strategy for holding schools accountable for education quality and outcomes (Sakamoto, 2021). Engaging parents in school management is viewed as an important mechanism for improving student achievement because parents have direct incentives to improve their child's education (Barrera-Osorio et al., 2009).

Sakamoto (2021) pointed out, parent participation in school management is unique in that it influences student learning through two channels. First, individual parents who participate in school management could obtain insider information about school, such as curriculum design and instructional/assessment policy, and build networks with school personnel and other parents. These parents may use these resources to provide optimal levels of learning support for their child at home (Hill & Taylor, 2004), for example, by providing effective homework help and private tutoring. Second, a group of parents

participating in school management could influence school decisions and change school policy and practice to improve the learning environment at school (Epstein, 1995). Due to its school-wide influence, this benefit accrues to even students whose parents do not participate in school management as spillover effects (Sakamoto, 2021).

In Pilas school district, the participation of parents in school management had not been formally assessed, thus no reference of information for the generation of plans for the enhancement of their participation could be initiated, to consequently influence student learning. Thus, this study to evaluate the parent participation in school management in Pilas District.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Theory of Participation of Mark S. Reed, et al. (2017), the Parent Engagement Model of McKenna and Millen (2013), and the Theory of School-Based Management formulated by David Gamage (2006) served as the theoretical frameworks of this study on the parent participation in school management in Pilas District.

The Theory of Participation of Mark S. Reed, et al. (2017) explains how the outcomes of stakeholder and public engagement in management are explained by context, process design, the management of power dynamics and scalar fit.

“Context” shows how the outcomes of stakeholder and public engagement are affected by (mainly local) socio-economic, cultural and institutional contexts within which it is enacted. Examples of specific contextual factors that may significantly affect the success of an engagement process include the existence of a participatory culture and former experiences of engagement (whether successful or unsuccessful) and available resources.

“Design” shows how a number of process design factors can increase the likelihood that engagement leads to desired outcomes, across a wide range of socio-cultural, political, economic and biophysical contexts. In particular, engagement processes that systematically represent relevant public and stakeholder interests and provide transparent opportunities to influence outcomes based on multiple knowledge sources are more likely to deliver beneficial outcomes, across a wide range of contexts.

The effectiveness of engagement is significantly influenced by “Power” dynamics, the values of participants and their epistemologies i.e. the way they construct knowledge and which types of knowledge they consider valid. Poor management of power dynamics is one of the major reasons for engagement failing to deliver outcomes. Professional facilitation and mediation can significantly reduce the likelihood of conflict and where conflicts have already started, can help reduce or resolve conflicts through engagement with and management of power dynamics between participants.

“Scalar fit”. Outcomes from engagement are highly scale-dependent over space and time. Contextual values, such as preferences for one option or another, may change over short timescales, but the extent to which engagement (via deliberation) shapes the values of participants is highly dependent on the temporal scales over which engagement occurs. For engagement to deliver desired outcomes, representation of stakeholder interests and decision-making power needs to match a spatial scale relevant to the scale of the issues being considered. In this way, those with national interests and decision-making power will be involved in national decisions but local actors will be empowered to engage in issues at scales more relevant to their interests.

This study on the parent participation in school management is securely founded on ‘The Theory of Participation’ which explains how the outcomes of stakeholder and public engagement in management are explained by context, process design, the management of power dynamics and scalar fit. Accordingly, “Context” shows how the outcomes of stakeholder and public engagement are affected by (mainly local) socio-economic, cultural and institutional contexts within which it is enacted – that’s mainly in the context of Pilas District community. “Design” would explain how a number of process design factors can increase the likelihood that engagement In particular, engagement processes that systematically represent relevant public and stakeholder interests and provide transparent opportunities – that’s representing the relevant interests of, and opportunities for the parents of pupils in Pilas District. The effectiveness of engagement is significantly influenced by “Power” dynamics, the values of participants and the way they construct knowledge and which types of knowledge they consider valid – the values and knowledge of the parents of pupils in Pilas District. “Scalar fit” highlights the outcomes from engagement are highly scale-dependent over space and time, such as those with national interests and decision-making power will be involved in national decisions, but local actors will be empowered to engage in issues at scales more relevant to their interests – the local actors are the educational stakeholders in the district, which would desirably include parents.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The socio-demographic characteristics of the Parents-Teachers Community Association (PTCA) Officers of public elementary schools in Pilas District served as the independent variables of this study in terms of: age, gender, and highest educational attainment.

As dependent variable of the study, the parent participation in school management in Pilas District was determined adopting the questionnaire developed by Federico G. Jaboya (2018) in his study ‘Participation of Stakeholders in the Implementation of the Enhanced-School Based Management (SBM)’ focusing on the assessment of the stakeholders’ participation in the enhanced SBM in terms of: school governance, curriculum enhancement, community development, and student activities.

The implication of this study is to enhance the active parent participation in school management in Pilas District.

Figure 1 shows the schematic diagram of the conceptual framework of the study.

FIGURE 1. Schematic Diagram of the Conceptual Framework of the Study

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The purpose of the study was to determine the parent participation in school management in Pilas District. It sought answers the following specific questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the Parents-Teachers Community Association (PTCA) Officers of public elementary schools in Pilas District, in terms of:
 - a. Age;
 - b. Gender; and
 - c. Highest Educational Attainment?
2. What is the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, in terms of:
 - a. School Governance;
 - b. Curriculum Enhancement;
 - c. Community Development; and
 - d. Student Activities?

3. Are there significant differences between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, if the data are grouped according to:
- Age;
 - Gender; and
 - Highest Educational Attainment?

STATEMENT OF THE HYPOTHESIS

There are no significant differences between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, if the data are grouped according to Age, Gender, and Highest Educational Attainment.

SCOPE AND LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

This study determined the parent participation in school management in Pilas District. The respondents of the study were the **Parents-Teachers Community Association (PTCA) Officers** of public elementary schools in Pilas District.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

Comprising this chapter are the views, perceptions, and researches conducted that are related to this study on the parent participation in school management in Pilas District.

RELATED LITERATURE

Parent involvement - Parenting Styles and Dimensions

Parent involvement often refer to parenting styles or dimensions when examining the theoretical background behind parental involvement (e.g., Cooper, Lindsay, & Nye, 2000). As stated previously, these styles and dimensions assist in informing about parents' influences over children and their overall development. It has been documented through research that parents have different ways of interacting with their children, especially in terms of the manner in which parents set rules for, discipline, or monitor the child and his or her behavior. These ways of interacting have been described as parenting styles as well as dimensions of parenting. The central parenting styles described in many research studies include authoritarian, authoritative, permissive, and, to a somewhat lesser degree, rejecting neglectful (Baumrind, 1991). These four styles are defined by Baumrind (1991) in the following manner: Authoritarian – “parents are demanding and directive, but not responsive. They are obedience- and status-oriented, and expect their orders to be obeyed without explanation. They provide an orderly environment, and a clear set of regulations, and monitor their children’s activities carefully”. Authoritative – “parents are both demanding and responsive. They monitor and impart clear standards for their children’s conduct. They are assertive, but not intrusive or restrictive. Their disciplinary methods are supportive rather than punitive. They want their children to be assertive as well as socially responsible, and self-regulated as well as cooperative”. Permissive – “or nondirective parents are more responsive than they are demanding. They are nontraditional and lenient, do not require mature behavior, allow considerable self-regulation, and avoid confrontation”. Rejecting-neglecting – “or disengaged parents are neither demanding nor responsive. They do not structure and monitor, and are not supportive, but may be actively rejecting or else neglect their childrearing responsibilities altogether”. Other styles, similar to permissive and neglectful, that are described in research include indulgent and disengaged, respectively (Lamborn, Mounts, Steinberg, & Dornbusch, 1991; Steinberg, 1996). These and other studies have determined that the most advantageous style of parenting for children’s development is authoritative. With this form of parenting, the parent is firm and sets limits, but provides the child with reasoning for their decisions. Additionally, the parent is supportive and encourages the child’s autonomy. Research also has looked at the maternal and paternal differences in parenting styles in both adolescents and late adolescents (e.g., McGillicuddy-De Lisi & De Lisi, 2007; McKinney & Renk, 2008). Types of dimensions described in research studies include acceptance versus rejection, firmness versus leniency, and autonomy versus control (Baumrind 1989; Lamborn et al., 1991; Steinberg, 1996) as well as parental support, behavioral control, and psychological control (Bean, Bush, McKenry, & Wilson, 2003).

III. RESEARCH DESIGN AND PROCEDURES

This chapter discusses the Research Design and Procedures in conducting this research on the parent participation in school management in Pilas District.

THE RESEARCH METHOD

The descriptive method of research was used to determine the extent of parent participation in school management in Pilas District.

THE SUBJECTS AND RESPONDENTS OF THE STUDY

The subjects of the study were the One Hundred Thirty (130) **Parents-Teachers Community Association (PTCA) Officers** of the Thirteen (13) Public Elementary Schools in Pilas District.

The respondents' sample size was determined using the Slovin's Formula. In this study, with a desired margin of error of 5%, the sample size was supposedly Ninety-Nine (99), but the quotient of dividing this by the number of schools in the district evenly, which is Thirteen (13), would yield 7.6. Thus, rounding it off, would result to Eight (8) respondents per school, making the total number of respondents to One Hundred Four (104) **Parents-Teachers Community Association (PTCA) Officers** of public elementary schools in Pilas District.

A simple random sampling was adopted in this study. To identify the respondents in each school, a random sampling of the **Parents-Teachers Community Association (PTCA) Officers** of public elementary schools in Pilas District was conducted in each school.

Table 1 shows the distribution of the population and sample of the study, in each public elementary schools in Pilas District.

Table 1: The Distribution of the PTCA Officers Population and Respondents in Pilas District

SCHOOL	POPULATION	RESPONDENTS
Panducan Elementary School	10	8
Tausan Elementary School	10	8
Lubukan Elementary School	10	8
Lukbungsud Elementary School	10	8
Lukbaldaya Primary School	10	8
Salisa Primary School	10	8
Kainahan Primary School	10	8
Mananggal Primary School	10	8
Baluk Baluk Elementary School	10	8
Palahangan Elementary School	10	8
Dasalan Elementary School	10	8
Sangbay Big Elementary School	10	8
Sangbay Small Elementary School	10	8
TOTAL	130	104

THE RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

To determine the extent of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, a two - part survey questionnaire was used.

One part gathered information on the socio-demographic characteristics of the Parents-Teachers Community Association (PTCA) Officers of public elementary schools in Pilas District.

Part two of the questionnaire determined the extent of parent participation in school management in Pilas District adapting the questionnaire developed by Federico G. Jaboya (2018) in his study 'Participation of Stakeholders in the Implementation of the Enhanced-School Based Management (SBM)' focusing on the assessment of the stakeholders' participation in the enhanced SBM in terms of: school governance, curriculum enhancement, community development, and student activities.

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The PTCA Officer-respondents were asked to respond to specific statements on a Four-point Likert scale to rate the extent to which they participate in school management utilizing the scale:

Rating	Extent of Participation
1	- Not Participate (N)
2	- Least Participate (L)
3	- Moderately Participate (M)
4	- Fully Participate (F)

The following scale was used for the interpretation of the weighted mean:

Scale	Extent	Level of Participation
1.00 – 1.49 =	Not Participate	No Participation
1.50 – 2.49 =	Least Participate	Low Participation
2.50 – 3.49 =	Moderately Participate	Average Participation
3.50 – 4.00 =	Fully Participate	High Participation

The interpretation of the results would be:

A mean rating of 1.00 to 1.49 would be interpreted that the parents “Don’t Participate” in the stated activity/task/role. This means that there is “No Participation” in the indicated activity/task/role of the parents in school management in Pilas District.

A mean rating of 1.50 to 2.49 would be interpreted that the parents “Least Participate” in the stated activity/task/role. This denotes that there is “Low Participation” in the indicated activity/task/role of the parents in school management in Pilas District.

A mean rating of 2.50 to 3.49 would be interpreted that the parents “Moderately Participate” in the stated activity/task/role. This signifies that there is “Average Participation” in the indicated activity/task/role of the parents in school management in Pilas District.

A mean rating of 3.50 to 4.00 would be interpreted that the parents “Fully Participate” in the stated activity/task/role. This indicates that there is “High Participation” in the indicated activity/task/role of the parents in school management in Pilas District.

THE INSTRUMENT VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY

The instrument developed by Federico G. Jaboya (2018) in his study ‘Participation of Stakeholders in the Implementation of the Enhanced-School Based Management (SBM)’ focusing on the assessment of the stakeholders’ participation in the enhanced SBM, had gone through a validation and reliability process.

In determining the content validity of the instrument, the questionnaire items were subjected to a validity process. They were rated by Three (3) experts in the field of education for content validity. They rated the instrument items for their suitability as instrument item. The scale below was utilized:

Rating	Suitability
1	Not Suitable
2	Needs Revision
3	Suitable

An F-test was then conducted. It resulted to an F-value of 1.917 and a p-value of 0.341, which showed no significant differences between the ratings of the evaluators, therefore, the instrument can be considered as valid in determining the extent of parent participation in school management in Pilas District.

To establish the reliability of the questionnaire, an inter-item analysis was conducted. The questionnaire was administered to thirty (30) Elementary School teachers in the different public elementary schools in Lantawan School District. The

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reliability test yielded a Cronbach’s Alpha value of 0.990. In accordance with DeVellis’ Reliability Scale (1991), the score classifies as “very good” reliability.

DATA GATHERING PROCEDURE

The researcher sought permission from the Pilas School District Supervisor to conduct this study. Granted the request, the questionnaires were distributed to the PTCA Officer-respondents from the schools in the district.

STATISTICAL TREATMENT OF DATA

To determine the socio-demographic profile of the Parents-Teachers Community Association (PTCA) Officers of public elementary schools in Pilas District, the frequency, and percent were used.

To determine the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, the weighted mean and ranking were used.

To determine the significant difference between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, if the data are grouped according to gender, the t-Test was used.

To determine the significant differences between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, if the data are grouped according to age, and highest educational attainment, the One - Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

As per provision of the letter of informed consent, the researcher guaranteed the respondents from emotional, psychological, and physical harm. Their sense of independence in answering questions was at all times observed. The survey respondents’ anonymity, privacy, and confidentiality were protected, in all instances of extracting the needed data.

IV. PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter covers the presentation, analyses and interpretation of the data gathered on the parent participation in school management in Pilas District.

Socio-Demographic Profile of the PTCA Officers

Shown in Table 2 is the profile of the Parents-Teachers Community Association (PTCA) Officers of public elementary schools in Pilas District.

Table 2: Profile of the PTCA Officers (N = 104)

DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLE	FREQUENCY (N)	PERCENT (%)
A. AGE		
25 years or less	2	1.9
26 to 30 years old	19	18.3
31 to 35 years old	22	21.2
36 yrs and above	61	58.6
B. GENDER		
Male	28	26.9
Female	76	73.1
C. HIGHEST EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT		
Did not finish Elementary School	10	9.6
Elementary Graduate	46	44.2
High School Graduate	33	31.7
Baccalaureate Degree	11	10.6
Master’s Degree	4	3.9
Doctorate Degree	0	0

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Majority of the Parents-Teachers Community Association (PTCA) Officers of public elementary schools in Pilas District are aged 36 years old and above (58.6%). Mostly are female (73.1%). About two fifths of them are elementary graduates (44.2%).

Extents of Parent Participation in School Management

Tables 3 to 6 show the means, descriptions, and ranks of the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, in terms of School Governance, Curriculum Enhancement, Community Development, and Student Activities.

Table 3: Means, Descriptions, and Ranks of the Parents' Ratings in Terms of School Governance (N = 104)

A. SCHOOL GOVERNANCE	MEAN	DESCRIPTION	RANK
Activity/Task/Role 1	2.663	Moderately Participate	1
Activity/Task/Role 2	2.615	Moderately Participate	2
Activity/Task/Role 3	2.481	Least Participate	4
Activity/Task/Role 4	2.587	Moderately Participate	3
Activity/Task/Role 5	2.250	Least Participate	5
AVERAGE	2.519	Moderately Participate	NA

In the area of School Governance, the parents rated that they 'Least Participate' in the following activities/tasks/roles in the management of their child/ren's school:

1. Activity/Task/Role 5 - Examine the whereabouts of the school funds and MOOE allocation and liquidation
2. Activity/Task/Role 3 - Involve in the School Improvement Plan formulation

The parents rated that they 'Moderately Participate' in the following activities/tasks/roles in the management of their child/ren's school:

1. Activity/Task/Role 1 - Participate in the formation of School Governing Council (SGC)
2. Activity/Task/Role 2 - Support the selection of School Governing Council (SGC) members
3. Activity/Task/Role 4 - Involve in the School Improvement Plan implementation

On the average, the parents rated that they 'Moderately Participate' in the management of their child/ren's school, in the area of School Governance. Their level of participation is 'Average'.

Table 4: Means, Descriptions, and Ranks of the Parents' Ratings in Terms of Curriculum Enhancement (N = 104)

B. CURRICULUM ENHANCEMENT	MEAN	DESCRIPTION	RANK
Activity/Task/Role 6	2.433	Least Participate	2
Activity/Task/Role 7	2.394	Least Participate	3
Activity/Task/Role 8	2.510	Moderately Participate	1
AVERAGE	2.445	Least Participate	NA

In the area of Curriculum Enhancement, the parents rated that they 'Least Participate' in the following activities/tasks/roles in the management of their child/ren's school:

1. Activity/Task/Role 7 - Contribute in the planning of the curricular offering
2. Activity/Task/Role 6 - Support the localization and customization of the curriculum

The parents rated that they 'Moderately Participate' in activity/task/role 8, which is to 'assist in enhancing areas in the curriculum which needs improvement'.

On the average, the parents rated that they 'Least Participate' in the management of their child/ren's school, in the area of Curriculum Enhancement. Their level of participation in the area of Curriculum Enhancement is 'Low'.

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Table 5: Means, Descriptions, and Ranks of the Parents' Ratings in Terms of Community Development (N = 104)

C. COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT	MEAN	DESCRIPTION	RANK
Activity/Task/Role 9	2.865	Moderately Participate	1
Activity/Task/Role 10	2.769	Moderately Participate	3
Activity/Task/Role 11	2.808	Moderately Participate	2
AVERAGE	2.814	Moderately Participate	NA

In the area of Community Development, the parents rated that they 'Moderately Participate' in all activities/tasks/roles in the management of their child/ren's school, as follows:

1. Activity/Task/Role 9 - Formulate plans for community improvement
2. Activity/Task/Role 11 - Encourage activities that ensure application of learning to homes and communities
3. Activity/Task/Role 10 - Establish strong relationship with other schools

On the average, the parents rated that they 'Moderately Participate' in activities/tasks/roles in the management of their child/ren's school, in the area of Community Development. Their level of participation in this area is 'Average'.

Table 6: Means, Descriptions, and Ranks of the Parents' Ratings in Terms of Student Activities (N = 104)

D. STUDENT ACTIVITIES	MEAN	DESCRIPTION	RANK
Activity/Task/Role 12	2.519	Moderately Participate	2
Activity/Task/Role 13	2.490	Least Participate	3
Activity/Task/Role 14	2.529	Moderately Participate	1
Activity/Task/Role 15	2.462	Least Participate	4
AVERAGE	2.500	Moderately Participate	NA

In the area of Student Activities, the parents rated that they 'Least Participate' in the following activities/tasks/roles in the management of their child/ren's school:

1. Activity/Task/Role 15 - Draw up plans for class activities with teachers
2. Activity/Task/Role 13 - Assist in the conduct of small group study for the enrichment/remedial program of the pupils

The parents rated that they 'Moderately Participate' in the following activities/tasks/roles in the management of their child/ren's school:

1. Activity/Task/Role 14 - Assist remediation and enrichment classes
2. Activity/Task/Role 12 - Provide inputs in enrichment/remedial programs

On the average, the parents rated that they 'Moderately Participate' in activities/tasks/roles in the management of their child/ren's school, in the area of Student Activities. Their level of participation in this area is 'Average'.

Table 7 shows the summary of the means, descriptions, and ranks of the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, in terms of School Governance, Curriculum Enhancement, Community Development, and Student Activities.

Table 7: Summary of Means, Descriptions, and Ranks of the Extents of Parent Participation in School Management (N = 104)

AREA	MEAN	DESCRIPTION	RANK
A. School Governance	2.519	Moderately Participate	2
B. Curriculum Enhancement	2.445	Least Participate	4
C. Community Development	2.814	Moderately Participate	1
D. Student Activities	2.500	Moderately Participate	3
OVERALL	2.570	Moderately Participate	NA

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The parents rated that they ‘Least Participate’ in activities/tasks/roles in the management of their child/ren’s school, in Curriculum Enhancement. Their level of participation in this area is ‘Low’.

The parents rated that they ‘Moderately Participate’ in activities/tasks/roles in the management of their child/ren’s school, in the following areas, which level is considered ‘Average’:

1. Community Development
2. School Governance
3. Student Activities

Overall, the parents rated that they ‘Moderately Participate’ in activities/tasks/roles in the management of their child/ren’s school.

The level of parent participation in school management in Pilas District is ‘Average’.

The parents ‘least participate’ in the following activities/tasks/roles in the management of their child/ren’s school:

1. Activity/Task/Role 5 - Examine the whereabouts of the school funds and MOOE allocation and liquidation
2. Activity/Task/Role 7 - Contribute in the planning of the curricular offering
3. Activity/Task/Role 6 - Support the localization and customization of the curriculum
4. Activity/Task/Role 15 - Draw up plans for class activities with teachers
5. Activity/Task/Role 3 - Involve in the School Improvement Plan formulation
6. Activity/Task/Role 13 - Assist in the conduct of small group study for the enrichment/remedial program of the pupils

The parents ‘Moderately Participate’ in the following activities/tasks/roles in the management of their child/ren’s school:

1. Activity/Task/Role 9 - Formulate plans for community improvement
2. Activity/Task/Role 11 - Encourage activities that ensure application of learning to homes and communities
3. Activity/Task/Role 10 - Establish strong relationship with other schools
4. Activity/Task/Role 1 – Participate in the formation of School Governing Council (SGC)
5. Activity/Task/Role 2 - Support the selection of School Governing Council (SGC) members
6. Activity/Task/Role 4 - Involve in the School Improvement Plan implementation
7. Activity/Task/Role 14 - Assist remediation and enrichment classes
8. Activity/Task/Role 12 - Provide inputs in enrichment/remedial programs
9. Activity/Task/Role 8 - Assist in enhancing areas in the curriculum which needs improvement

A. Significant Differences Between the Extents of Parent Participation in School Management, if Data are Grouped According to Age

Table 8: F -Values and Levels of Significance of the ANOVA Between the Means Grouped by Age

AREA	F -Values	Level of Significance	Remarks
A. School Governance	.144	.933	No significant difference @ $\alpha = 0.05$
B. Curriculum Enhancement	.283	.837	No significant difference @ $\alpha = 0.05$
C. Community Development	.720	.542	No significant difference @ $\alpha = 0.05$
D. Student Activities	.318	.812	No significant difference @ $\alpha = 0.05$
OVERALL	.225	.879	No significant difference @ $\alpha = 0.05$

Tested at 0.05-level of significance, there are no significant differences between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, in the areas of School Governance, Curriculum Enhancement, Community Development, and Student Activities, if the data are grouped according to age.

Overall, tested at 0.05-level of significance, there are no significant differences between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, if the data are grouped according to age.

The extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, are on the same level, regardless of age.

B. Significant Differences Between the Extents of Parent Participation in School Management, if Data are Grouped According to Gender

Table 9: T - Values and Levels of Significance of the t-Test Between the Means Grouped by Gender

AREA	T -Values	Level of Significance	Remarks
A. School Governance	-488	.627	No significant difference @ $\alpha = 0.05$
B. Curriculum Enhancement	-744	.461	No significant difference @ $\alpha = 0.05$
C. Community Development	1.169	.246	No significant difference @ $\alpha = 0.05$
D. Student Activities	-1.022	.312	No significant difference @ $\alpha = 0.05$
OVERALL	-365	.716	No significant difference @ $\alpha = 0.05$

Tested at 0.05-level of significance, there are no significant differences between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, in the areas of School Governance, Curriculum Enhancement, Community Development, and Student Activities, if the data are grouped according to gender.

Overall, tested at 0.05-level of significance, there are no significant differences between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, if the data are grouped according to gender. The extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, are on the same level for both the male and female parent-respondents.

C. Significant Differences Between the Extents of Parent Participation in School Management, if Data are Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment

Table 10 shows the F-values and levels of significance of the ANOVA on the significant difference between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, if the data are grouped according to Highest Educational Attainment.

Table 10: F -Values and Levels of Significance of the ANOVA between the Means Grouped by Highest Educational Attainment

AREA	F -Values	Level of Significance	Remarks
A. School Governance	5.602	.000	Significant difference @ $\alpha = 0.05$
B. Curriculum Enhancement	8.701	.000	Significant difference @ $\alpha = 0.05$
C. Community Development	4.373	.003	Significant difference @ $\alpha = 0.05$
D. Student Activities	8.034	.000	Significant difference @ $\alpha = 0.05$
OVERALL	7.684	.000	Significant difference @ $\alpha = 0.05$

Tested at 0.05-level of significance, there are significant differences between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, in the areas of School Governance, Curriculum Enhancement, Community Development, and Student Activities, if the data are grouped according to the highest educational attainment of the parents.

Overall, tested at 0.05-level of significance, there are significant differences between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, if the data are grouped according to the highest educational attainment of the parents.

The extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, are on different levels, depending on the Highest Educational Attainment of parents.

The Extents of Parent Participation in School Management in Pilas District, if Data are Grouped According to the Highest Educational Attainment of Parents

Table 11 shows the means of the ratings of parents on their extents of participation in school management in Pilas District, if classified according to Highest Educational Attainment.

Table 11: The Mean Ratings of Parents on Their Extents of Participation in School Management in Pilas District, if Classified According to Highest Educational Attainment (N = 104)

AREA OF SCHOOL MANAGEMENT	HIGHEST EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT				
	Did not finish Elementary School	Elementary Graduate	High School Graduate	Baccalaureate Degree	Master's Degree
A. School Governance	2.140	2.452	2.352	3.255	3.600
B. Curriculum Enhancement	2.000	2.283	2.374	3.303	3.667
C. Community Development	2.500	2.746	2.677	3.424	3.834
D. Student Activities	2.175	2.304	2.432	3.409	3.625
OVERALL	2.204	2.447	2.459	3.348	3.681

The parents with master’s degree have the highest extent or level of participation in all areas of school management in Pilas District, compared to parents with lower educational attainment. They fully participate in activities/tasks/roles in the management of their child/ren’s school, in all areas. They are most active in community development.

The parents who did not finish elementary school have the lowest extent or level of participation in all areas of school management in Pilas District, compared to parents with higher educational attainment. The group’s highest level of participation was in community development, which was just moderate. They least participate in all other areas of school management.

In general, the higher the educational attainment of the parents, the higher are their extents or levels of participation in the management of their child/ren’s school.

V. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter consists of the summary of findings, the conclusions, and the recommendations of this study.

Summary of Findings

This study was conducted to determine the parent participation in school management in Pilas District. The findings of the study are as follows:

I - The Socio-Demographic Profile of the PTCA Officers

Majority of the Parents-Teachers Community Association (PTCA) Officers of public elementary schools in Pilas District are aged 36 years old and above. Mostly are female. Forty-four-point two percent (44.2%) of them are elementary graduates.

II - The Extents of Parent Participation in School Management

A. School Governance

In the area of School Governance, the parents rated that they ‘Least Participate’ in the following activities/tasks/roles in the management of their children’s school:

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3. Examine the whereabouts of the school funds and MOOE allocation and liquidation (Mean = 2.250)
4. Involve in the School Improvement Plan formulation (Mean = 2.587)

The parents rated that they 'Moderately Participate' in the following activities/tasks/roles in the management of their children's school:

1. Participate in the formation of School Governing Council (SGC) (Mean = 2.663)
2. Support the selection of School Governing Council (SGC) members (Mean = 2.615)
3. Involve in the School Improvement Plan implementation (Mean = 2.587)

On the average, the parents rated that they 'Moderately Participate' in the management of their children's school, in the area of School Governance. Their level of participation is 'Average' (Mean=2.519).

B. Curriculum Enhancement

In the area of Curriculum Enhancement, the parents rated that they 'Least Participate' in the following activities/tasks/roles in the management of their children's school:

1. Contribute in the planning of the curricular offering (Mean = 2.394)
2. Support the localization and customization of the curriculum (Mean = 2.433)

The parents rated that they 'Moderately Participate' in 'assisting to enhance areas in the curriculum which needs improvement' (Mean = 2.510).

On the average, the parents rated that they 'Least Participate' in the management of their children's school, in the area of Curriculum Enhancement (Mean = 2.445). Their level of participation in the area of Curriculum Enhancement is 'Low'.

C. Community Development

In the area of Community Development, the parents rated that they 'Moderately Participate' in all activities/tasks/roles in the management of their children's school, as follows:

1. Formulate plans for community improvement (Mean = 2.865)
2. Encourage activities that ensure application of learning to homes and communities (Mean = 2.808)
3. Establish strong relationship with other schools (Mean = 2.769)

On the average, the parents rated that they 'Moderately Participate' in activities/tasks/roles in the management of their children's school, in the area of Community Development (Mean = 2.814). Their level of participation in this area is 'Average'.

D. Student Activities

In the area of Student Activities, the parents rated that they 'Least Participate' in the following activities/tasks/roles in the management of their children's school:

1. Draw up plans for class activities with teachers (Mean = 2.462)
2. Assist in the conduct of small group study for the enrichment/remedial program of the pupils (Mean = 2.490)

The parents rated that they 'Moderately Participate' in the following activities/tasks/roles in the management of their children's school:

1. Assist remediation and enrichment classes (Mean = 2.529)
2. Provide inputs in enrichment/remedial programs (Mean = 2.519)

On the average, the parents rated that they 'Moderately Participate' in activities/tasks/roles in the management of their children's school, in the area of Student Activities (Mean = 2.500). Their level of participation in this area is 'Average'.

E. Overall

The parents rated that they ‘Least Participate’ in activities/tasks/roles in the management of their children’s school, in Curriculum Enhancement (Mean = 2.445). Their level of participation in this area is ‘Low’.

The parents rated that they ‘Moderately Participate’ in activities/tasks/roles in the management of their children’s school, in the following areas, which level is considered ‘Average’:

1. Community Development (Mean = 2.814)
2. School Governance (Mean = 2.519)
3. Student Activities (Mean = 2.500)

The parents rated that they ‘Moderately Participate’ in activities/tasks/roles in the management of their children’s school (Mean = 2.570).

The level of parent participation in school management in Pilas District is ‘Average’. They ‘least participate’ in the following activities/tasks/roles in the management of their children’s school:

1. Examine the whereabouts of the school funds and MOOE allocation and liquidation
2. Contribute in the planning of the curricular offering
3. Support the localization and customization of the curriculum
4. Draw up plans for class activities with teachers
5. Involve in the School Improvement Plan formulation
6. Assist in the conduct of small group study for the enrichment/remedial program of the pupils

The parents ‘Moderately Participate’ in the following activities/tasks/roles in the management of their children’s school:

1. Formulate plans for community improvement
2. Encourage activities that ensure application of learning to homes and communities
3. Establish strong relationship with other schools
4. Participate in the formation of School Governing Council (SGC)
5. Support the selection of School Governing Council (SGC) members
6. Involve in the School Improvement Plan implementation
7. Assist remediation and enrichment classes
8. Provide inputs in enrichment/remedial programs
9. Assist in enhancing areas in the curriculum which needs improvement

III - The Significant Differences Between the Extents of Parent Participation in School Management

A. If Data are Grouped According to Age

Tested at 0.05-level of significance, there are no significant differences between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, in the areas of School Governance, Curriculum Enhancement, Community Development, and Student Activities, if the data are grouped according to age.

Overall, tested at 0.05-level of significance, there are no significant differences between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, if the data are grouped according to age (Sig.=0.879).

The extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, are on the same level, regardless of age.

B. If Data are Grouped According to Gender

Tested at 0.05-level of significance, there are no significant differences between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, in the areas of School Governance, Curriculum Enhancement, Community Development, and Student Activities, if the data are grouped according to gender.

Overall, tested at 0.05-level of significance, there are no significant differences between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, if the data are grouped according to gender (Sig.=0.716).

The extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, are on the same level for both the male and female parent-respondents.

C. If Data are Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment

Tested at 0.05-level of significance, there are significant differences between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, in the areas of School Governance, Curriculum Enhancement, Community Development, and Student Activities, if the data are grouped according to the highest educational attainment of the parents.

Overall, tested at 0.05-level of significance, there are significant differences between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, if the data are grouped according to the highest educational attainment of the parents (Sig.=0.000).

The extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, are on different levels, depending on the Highest Educational Attainment of parents.

The parents with master's degree have the highest extent or level of participation in all areas of school management in Pilas District, compared to parents with lower educational attainment. They fully participate in activities/tasks/roles in the management of their children's school, in all areas. They are most active in community development.

The parents who did not finish elementary school have the lowest extent or level of participation in all areas of school management in Pilas District, compared to parents with higher educational attainment. The group's highest level of participation was in community development, which was just moderate. They least participate in all other areas of school management.

In general, the higher the educational attainment of the parents, the higher are their extents or levels of participation in the management of their children's school.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of this study:

The hypothesis that there are no significant differences between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, if the data are grouped according to:

1. Age, is accepted on the basis that, tested at 0.05-level of significance, there are no significant differences between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, if the data are grouped according to age.

Thus, the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, are on the same level, regardless of age.

2. Gender, is accepted on the basis that, tested at 0.05-level of significance, there are no significant differences between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, if the data are grouped according to gender.

Thus, the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, are on the same level for both the male and female parent-respondents.

3. Highest Educational Attainment, is rejected on the basis that, tested at 0.05-level of significance, there are significant differences between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, if the data are grouped according to the highest educational attainment of the parents.

Thus, the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, are on different levels, depending on the Highest Educational Attainment of parents. In general, the higher the educational attainment of the parents, the higher are their extents or levels of participation in the management of their children's school.

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are advanced:

To the Teachers

With the expanded perspective of the teachers on the importance of parental participation in managing schools, that is, the parents rated that they 'Moderately Participate' in activities/tasks/roles in the management of their children's school, in the area of Student Activities, it is recommended that teachers should further motivate and encourage the active participation of parents through participative decision - making, which could translate to school improvement and higher pupil achievement.

To the School Administrators/School Heads

The finding that the parents 'Moderately Participate' in the management of their children's school, in the area of School Governance, and their level of participation is 'Average' in this area, it is recommended that shared decision - making with the parents, be adopted by the school heads in practicing sound administrative management of the school towards a rational and acceptable policy formulation.

With the finding that the parents' participation is least in examining the whereabouts of the school funds and MOOE allocation and liquidation, it is recommended that such documents be accessible to parents, for transparent financial examinations. Likewise, with least involvement in the School Improvement Plan (SIP) formulation, parents be invited and encouraged to provide inputs with parental perspectives, in the generation of the SIP.

With the finding that there are significant differences between the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, if the data is grouped according to the highest educational attainment of the parents, thus the extents of parent participation in school management in Pilas District, are on different levels, depending on the Highest Educational Attainment of parents, it is recommended that school administrators in the district explore ways of enticing parents with low level of educational attainment to participate in activities/tasks/roles in the management of their children's school.

To the Parents

With the findings that: the parents' level of participation in the management of their children's school, in Curriculum Enhancement is 'Low'; their levels of participation in School Governance, Community Development, and Student Activities are 'Average'; and as a whole, their level of participation in school management is 'Average'. confirms the wanting involvement of parents in the management of schools. It is recommended that parents explore opportunities, improve their degrees of participation, and take a leadership role in school management.

To the Curriculum Designers

The finding on curriculum enhancement that the parents 'Least Participate' in the management of their children's school, in the area of Curriculum Enhancement, and their level of participation in this area is 'Low', it is recommended that curriculum planners solicit from parents, valuable inputs as to how the curriculum can be made acceptable to the parents and other stakeholders. Getting parents more involved, will further contribute to the generation of curricula which are localized and customized for Pilas District.

To the Department of Education

It is recommended that DepEd generate the necessary policies and plan the courses of action to be implemented at the school level, to increase the level of parent participation in managing schools, focusing on the following activities/tasks/roles where the parents 'least participate' in the management of their children's school:

1. Examine the whereabouts of the school funds and MOOE allocation and liquidation
2. Contribute in the planning of the curricular offering
3. Support the localization and customization of the curriculum
4. Draw up plans for class activities with teachers

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5. Involve in the School Improvement Plan formulation
6. Assist in the conduct of small group study for the enrichment/remedial program of the pupils

To Future Researchers

Utilizing the data and information gathered in this study as accurate baseline/reference for parental participation in managing schools, conduct similar researches in the future, with a broader scope and additional research variables.

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